

The Beneficial Role of Physical-Motor Activity in People with Neurodevelopmental Disorders / ASD
Dr. Julio Salazar Gonzales, 2026
NGO Actitud / Bioactitud

The United States National Library of Medicine, MedlinePlus, defines Autism Spectrum Disorders as mental disorders that affect behavior, communication, and social skills. It states that they appear before the age of two. The word “spectrum” means that autism presents a wide variety of symptoms. Autism symptoms range from mild to severe. Some children with ASD cannot function without the support of parents and caregivers. Others need less support and are able to live independently.

<https://medlineplus.gov/spanish/pruebas-de-laboratorio/evaluacion-de-trastornos-del-espectro-autista-tea/>

It is evident that the autism spectrum presents different varieties and types of behaviors, and regular therapy is basic for developing the abilities that allow people to reduce their symptoms and support them in daily activities. These include programs such as ABA behavior modification, speech therapy, occupational therapy, socialization therapy, and others. However, for many years physical activity was overlooked as a therapeutic tool. Today, however, we recognize through multiple studies that it is highly recommended as a fundamental part of an appropriate multifactorial therapeutic approach.

Since the 1980s, I have physically trained people with different abilities, as they are often colloquially called today. Among them, many of my students have been diagnosed with Down syndrome, intellectual disability, Autism Spectrum Disorder, and related conditions. My relationship with physical activity through the NGO Actitud in Lima, Peru, and with athletes with different abilities has allowed me to observe over time, especially in a sustained way, how beneficial physical activity is for better performance in all physical, emotional, and cognitive areas.

In recent years, various studies have frequently shown the tremendous importance of physical-motor and sports activities as early intervention therapy for people with Neurodevelopmental Disorders / ASD. For almost the last four decades, I have maintained the same position, having been an exceptional witness to very evident improvements not only in the physical-motor area, but also in behavior, socialization, and many other benefits that I will describe throughout this article.

Years ago, physical activity was considered irrelevant in the treatment or therapeutic interventions for ASD. Later, over the years, studies began to appear demonstrating the opposite and showing that it is, in fact, a highly recommended therapy.

Scientific evidence tells us that diagnostic and treatment strategies for Neurodevelopmental Disorders emphasize each individual’s cognitive and behavioral abilities. This is especially important when indicating therapies aimed at strengthening the areas in which the patient has the greatest difficulty.

Based on my experience, I can state that if a student with ASD does not learn to know and manage their own body, they will have greater difficulty understanding and properly managing the environment around them. It is true that today we know of many medical problems associated with ASD that greatly influence behavior and conduct, such as foods with a neuromodulatory effect, including the presence of opioid peptides in the diet; overstimulation or inhibition of key neurotransmitters involved in behavior; intestinal dysbiosis; general inflammation; heavy metal toxicity; sensory alterations; mitochondrial dysfunction; and many others related to each person’s biochemical individuality. However, in this article we will refer only to the relationship between physical activity and ASD and its benefits.

The benefits of physical activity in people with Neurodevelopmental Disorders or ASD are multiple. In light of the advances made in recent years in this field, we can determine that physical activity is a very important factor to consider for the development of cognitive, physical, and inclusive abilities. But you may be wondering how physical activity can benefit people with ASD, so we will explain this in greater detail.

The unequivocal expression of motor identity is movement, which is the translocation of the body in space, regulated by the Central Nervous System. Multiple studies around the world have shown that vigorous or intense exercise, performed frequently, is associated with a reduction in stereotypies, hyperactivity, aggression, self-injury, and destructive behaviors.

As early as 1995, Dr. P. Dennison, an educator and neuroscientist, stated in a published article that movement is the gateway to learning and that it awakens and activates many of our mental capacities. It integrates and fixes new information and experience in our neural networks; through it, we integrate and express our learning, our understanding, and ourselves.

In order to acquire knowledge, there must be movement, since this is the way our brain learns, and it evolves toward the prediction of movement on the path to achieving intelligence.

In 1999, the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) recommended physical exercise with a frequency of between three and five days per week in order to achieve significant improvements in anxiety disorders.

In 1999, I published the book *Abriendo Fronteras*, in which I presented the program of the same name. In that book, I mentioned the positive changes in behavior achieved through physical activity for people with ASD. This methodology and its development were created together with MSc Ana Luisa Molina. In the book, I presented some of the benefits of sports practice in people with ASD, including the following:

- **Emotional.** It determines the relationship between the coach, students, sports group members, and the environment or surroundings.
- **Cognitive.** Routines, sequences, and repetitions of exercises facilitate the development of muscular and mental memory.
- **Order, structure, and discipline.** Behaviors and attitudes aimed at developing rules and standards of physical and emotional conduct are encouraged.
- **Physical conditioning.** Development of the student's aerobic and anaerobic capacities, as well as correction of psychomotor disorders.
- **Chemical.** Physical exercise and proper breathing allow the regulation of serotonin and other important neurotransmitters in the brain.
- **Nervous system factors.** These occur through the recruitment of motor units and their muscular synchronization.
- **Nutritional.** Following appropriate nutritional guidelines according to the particular characteristics of each student.

Physical activity helps people who have learning difficulties because ease and skill in the motor field are basic for the development of other higher-level capacities. Bodily self-knowledge and subsequent control allow for a greater ability to communicate with the outside world. *Abriendo Fronteras*, Cecosami Publishing House, 1999, Dr. Julio Salazar Gonzales.

In 2004, a study was published stating that physical-sports practice appears to have a positive effect on mental health because it produces the release of endorphins, specifically beta-endorphins, which leads to a reduction in anxiety, depression, and stress. Any type of physical activity, whether low or high impact, releases these substances, which act directly on the brain, producing an immediate feeling of well-being and relaxation. They also inhibit the nerve fibers that transmit pain, generating analgesia and sedation.

Therefore, a state of euphoria can be achieved thanks to these “natural painkillers” or “happiness hormones” (Martinsen, 2004; Paffenbarger, Lee, and Leung, 2004).

Of course, this information is not new. There have been decades of research and publications highlighting these benefits. However, when it came to Neurodevelopmental Disorders, physical activity was not given the attention and importance it deserved as a cofactor within the therapy being used.

It is clear that these studies demonstrate benefits not only at the physical level but also at the psychological level and, importantly, at the level of brain biochemistry, where brain neurotransmitters have a great deal to do with our behavior and conduct. These chemical substances are responsible for our predisposition to the intensity of our psychological response.

Twenty-two years ago, we already had information related to the benefits produced by physical activity at the level of brain neurotransmitters. These benefits are very evident in the behavior and conduct of students with ASD who engage in sports practice frequently, as can be observed at the NGO Actitud in Lima, Peru, for more than 30 years. The NGO has a Behavior Modification Program through Physical Activity for people with ASD and related conditions, with very good results, especially sustained over time. This has become evident not only through physical-motor and behavioral observation and evaluation, but also through organic acid analyses performed on many students, showing greater production of serotonin in the body and a balance between activating and inhibitory neurotransmitters. It is important to emphasize that nutrition also plays a predominant role in neurotransmitter production.

Another important study on the benefits of physical-motor activities in children with ASD as an early intervention indicates that great benefits from physical practice were observed.

The 2020 review study *Fundamental Motor Skills Intervention for Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A 10-Year Narrative Review*, by Silvia Busti Ceccarelli, Camilla Ferrante, Erica Gazzola, Gian Marco Marzocchi, Maria Nobile, Massimo Molteni, and Alessandro Crippa, is relevant in this regard.

The primary objective of this pilot study was to measure the effectiveness of an intensive intervention involving motor skills, physical activity, and socialization in young children diagnosed with ASD. The results shed light on the importance of including motor or physical programming as part of the early intervention services provided to young children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. Leah Ketcheson, Janet Hauck, Dale Ulrich, affiliations expanded, PMID: 27354429.

This study states that, over the last decade, evidence has converged showing that motor impairment is one of the most consistent markers, together with social-communication difficulties, for Autism Spectrum Disorder. In fact, generalized movement abnormalities have been described in the context of ASD. These motor abnormalities could have critical implications for later cognitive and social development.

The results of the study refer to potentially significant improvements in motor skills after the intervention and highlight the importance of including motor activities in rehabilitation programs designed for children with ASD.

In 2020, the Autism Research Institute, ARI, of the University of Arizona published a study on physical activity and children with ASD, stating the following:

Physical Exercise and Autism

Autism Research Institute, ARI

Education and Asperger’s Syndrome, Learning Styles and Autism, Adulthood: Articles, School Years, Social Communication Skills — J. McEachin, PhD, Building Quality Education Programs

The conclusion of this study was that one of the most effective treatments for people with autism is exercise. Studies show that vigorous and strenuous exercise is related to a decrease in stereotyped, self-stimulatory behaviors, hyperactivity, aggression, self-injury, and destructive behaviors.

Vigorous exercise should include at least 20 minutes of aerobic activity three to four times per week; mild exercise, according to the study, does not provide major benefits. Many children with autism gain weight easily due to inactivity, and this weight gain brings additional problems.

In general, exercise is very important for physical and mental health. Numerous studies show that vigorous exercise is very beneficial in treatments for depression.

I strongly agree with the study, except that I do not agree with the claim that mild exercise does not provide major benefits. I substantially differ from this position because, in order to perform vigorous exercise, we must first train the student from the foundation with mild or moderate exercises that allow them to learn them correctly and internalize their use and frequency. We cannot perform vigorous exercises if we have not previously adapted to them in order to reach the intense phase of training. It is precisely during this adaptation process that great benefits are achieved, as the person begins to manage their body in a more appropriate and efficient way. It is a sensory-muscular process that is entirely necessary in order to function in a more organized and balanced manner. This allows us to later increase the complexity of the training until the benefits described above, related to vigorous exercise as mentioned in the article, are achieved.

The methodological concept of learning is fulfilled by following the principle that people learn through a process that moves from easy to difficult. They must follow the path from the beginning, that is, from primary or basic behaviors and movements, such as eye contact and following simple instructions, gross and fine motor activities, to more complex behaviors such as motor and verbal imitation.

In my more than 30 years of sports training practice with students with ASD, mild exercises are the foundation of the interaction between the student, teacher, classmates, and environment. Likewise, they allow students to develop abilities that will become more complex as they progress and master them, until eventually they are able to manage them properly and later perform them vigorously. Mild exercise is the necessary prior step for this purpose. In addition, benefits are achieved at the neurotransmitter level due to the effects, even if mild, of physical exercise.

Multiple studies referring to the effects and benefits of physical exercise on brain neurotransmitters are well known, since it causes the release of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, endorphins, dopamine, and norepinephrine. These molecules are known to be involved in emotions.

Different studies have also shown the influence of exercise on these brain neurotransmitters, which are also associated with the storage and retrieval of memory, as well as mood. In addition, these studies suggest that regular exercise can generate permanent structural changes in the brain. An increase in body temperature can also lead to relaxation and a better mood. Herrera, H. (2008), *Effect of Physical Exercise on the Production of Brain Neurotransmitters and Its Relationship with the Prevention of Addictions*. Regarding this last point, it should be emphasized that, in the case of people with ASD who present an altered microbiome due to a predominance of fungi and yeasts that feed on sugars, this can trigger addiction to sugar and to foods that contain it.

Among the great benefits of physical-motor and sports activities in people with ASD, we find affinity and relationships between the coach and group participants, where positive emotions and feelings produced by group integration occur very frequently due to the action that exercise has on neurotransmitters.

Positive emotional periods activate the so-called dopaminergic nuclei, releasing dopamine, which stimulates the ganglia and strengthens the synapses that are active at the time learning is acquired (Wise, Spinder, De & Gerbe, 1982). Physical activity allows neuroplasticity and its benefits for learning processes and bodily control, which have an impact on the physical and emotional behavior of people with ASD.

This means that emotional states are the anchor of the cognitive process known as emotional learning. If the arousal is pleasurable, neuronal connectivity will strengthen in the same way. Learning emerges in response to the stimulus of other people, developing preference for activities. Human self-regulation influences one's own emotions (Thompson, 1994; Gross, 2003).

Another important group of substances that increase with exercise are neurotrophic factors. Neurotrophic factors are a family of proteins that support neuron survival. These substances belong to a family of growth factors, which are a type of protein released into the bloodstream and capable of binding to receptors on certain cells in order to stimulate their survival, growth, or differentiation.

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor is increased by exercise, improving cognitive functions and generating functional changes in neurons. John Ratey, *The Revolutionary New Science of Exercise and the Brain*, *Newsweek*, March 19, 2007.

At this point, we can refer to cognitive neuroscience as the link between biological neural mechanisms and cognitive processes, such as memory, attention, and language, without leaving aside emotions. Its purpose is to study the relationship between brain activity, learning, and behavior (Matute, 2012).

Learning is closely linked to behavior because it changes perspectives and mental schemas, reorganizing information based on what is known and on lived experiences. Each individual adapts ways of learning according to their cognitive, adaptive, or sensory capacities, whether visual, auditory, or kinesthetic. Education must connect the importance of brain activity with teaching-learning processes. Navarrete, D. (2020), "The Brain and Learning," *Revista Atlante: Cuadernos de Educación y Desarrollo*, June 2020.

Learning processes are reinforced through physical activity, and these resources of knowledge and self-control allow the development of new capacities (J. Salazar, 2020).

Exercise reduces stress and anxiety, improving sleep, reaction time, memory, and other areas.

Stereotyped behaviors interfere with teaching, and exercise programs significantly improve intentionality in the classroom. Parents and teachers should consider including vigorous exercise programs within Individualized Education Programs (IEPs).

In 2020, a meta-analysis was published on the effects of physical activity interventions in children and adolescents with autism:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32192008/>

International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 2020 Mar 17; 17(6):1950. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17061950. Jinfeng Huang, Chunjie Du, Jianjin Liu, Guangxin Tan.

This article aimed to discuss the effects of physical activity interventions in children and adolescents with autism through a meta-analysis, so that it may serve as a reference for future relevant research on the same topic. Regarding the research methods, by searching CNKI, the China National Knowledge Infrastructure; Wang Fang Data; VIP Database for Chinese Technical Periodicals; PubMed; Scopus; Web of Science; and other databases, the study collected randomized controlled trials on physical activity intervention in children and adolescents with autism. Review Manager 5.3 software was used to process and analyze the outcome indicators of the literature. As for the results, a total of 12 articles and 492 research subjects were selected. The results of the meta-analysis show that physical activity had a

significant positive impact on the social interaction ability, motor skills, and degree of autism in autistic children, as well as on the social and communication skills of autistic adolescents.

On the other hand, physical activity did not have a significant effect on stereotyped behavior in autistic children and adolescents. In conclusion, physical activity intervention is beneficial for children and adolescents with autism, and continuous physical activity intervention can produce a greater intervention effect.

The meta-analysis concludes that physical activity provides great and multiple benefits in children and adolescents with autism. It also states that stereotyped behaviors did not show significant benefits. Regarding this last point, I substantially differ because, in my more than 30 years of practice using physical activity with people with autism, stereotyped behaviors decrease substantially over time. I believe that, since these behaviors are the product of multiple triggering factors, these factors were not properly identified as precursors of such behaviors. If physical activity is properly directed, the emotional self-control produced by the benefits in neurotransmitters, as I mentioned earlier, will lead to a decrease in stereotypies at the biochemical level. In addition, proper muscular control also allows control over stereotyped movements, thereby also helping to modify behavior.

In conclusion, through the facts presented and supported by multiple studies, we can conclude that physical and sports activity is a highly appropriate tool for achieving great benefits in people with ASD and should be a fundamental part of the person's integrative therapy. It is time to consider it an important part of programs aimed at developing their abilities and enjoying physical and sports participation in an inclusive way.

I am convinced of the behavioral benefits of physical activity in people with autism. It is entirely viable and will provide a valuable tool in the future. The benefits of physical activity are of great usefulness for the development of multiple abilities, including physical-motor, cognitive, inclusive, and social abilities, among others described earlier in this article. I hope more research studies will be conducted on this behavioral topic, allowing for the demonstration and foundations that support physical intervention in behavior modification in people with autism, among the multiple benefits it provides.